

Palaeognath evolution: The untold story

Koen A. Claeys

Independent researcher - Ghent, Belgium

Correspondence: kclaeyspaleo@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0007-3405-8787

ABSTRACT

The Palaeognathae containing the extant running birds and the flying tinamous form the sister clade to all other extant birds, but until present, much mystery remains around their evolutionary history. Currently, the hypothesis that finds most agreement among bird paleontologists involves a spectacular sixfold convergent evolution from a smaller flying bird towards a large flightless body plan. This hypothesis includes a rather recent origin of the Palaeognathae, long after their land masses were isolated by oceans, and dispersal to these lands by flight. However, the alternative to this hypothesis has become severely underappreciated in modern literature, even though it could form an explanation for many unresolved issues concerning the origin and geographic distribution of the Palaeognathae. The last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae could have been a running bird, and flight originated in the tinamou lineage independently of the flight origin of the other birds. This alternative hypothesis would require the continental vicariance hypothesis to be restored to explain the distribution of these running birds on their different islands and continents. The origin of the Palaeognathae would have been much earlier than what was previously estimated based on arbitrarily chosen maximum divergence priors. In this critical review, the arguments in favour of both hypotheses are thoroughly investigated and compared. It is shown that a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae has been systematically rejected based on assumptions, biased approach and even wrong methodologies. The available data as well as new arguments and results from a new ancestral state reconstruction seem to be strongly in favour of a flightless last common ancestor. The enormous potential consequences of this neglected hypothesis are highlighted in context of the origin of running birds, but more importantly, the evolution of birds and other feathered dinosaurs. Most notably, it is shown that all modern phylogenetic studies on the origin of the Neornithes contain an important taxon bias due to the outdated assumption that the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a flying animal. A conservative unifying hypothesis that at present has not been rejected by any unbiased phylogenetic analysis is explored. It is suggested that this hypothesis, which needs to be properly tested in future work, might explain many enigmatic aspects about bird evolution including biogeography of basal Neornithes and the differential extinction of the dinosaurs at the end of the Cretaceous.

Keywords: Palaeognathae MRCA, origin of birds, evolution of flight, continental vicariance, ancestral state reconstruction, divergence times.

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95 I. Introduction

96 Few topics in evolutionary biology seem to spark so much controversy as the evolutionary history of
97 birds. Morphology-based phylogenies for example are plagued by convergent evolution and
98 character non-independence up to the point that the most parsimonious phylogenies are strongly
99 different from DNA-based phylogenies. Furthermore, the fossil record contains large gaps, and the
100 two basal clades of the neornithines (extant birds) have an estimated origin that is much older than
101 their oldest fossils. Additionally, literature on fossil and extant birds is filled with opposing views on
102 divergence times, phylogenetic relations, ancestral states and dispersal mechanisms. In this work,
103 the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae is used as a starting point to explore a new view on
104 bird evolution. Firstly, the evidence in favour of a flying last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae
105 is critically reviewed by pointing out flaws in methodology and by providing new and solid evidence
106 that goes against the current views. Additionally, the far-reaching potential consequences of the
107 presented evidence are discussed, and it is shown that an old and conservative hypothesis on the
108 origin of the origin of the Palaeognathae has never been properly rejected. Ultimately, a simple
109 unifying hypothesis is proposed that would mean a radical change of the currently established views
110 on bird evolution. It is shown that this hypothesis has never been properly rejected, and it is
111 suggested how future unbiased analyses should be designed to properly test this hypothesis. The
112 general goal of this review is to challenge the established views on the evolution of Palaeognathae
113 and more generally the Neornithes by pointing out flaws that have lead to overconfident
114 conclusions, but also by means of new evidence in favour of a radically different, yet simple and
115 conservative hypothesis. This unifying hypothesis will need to be tested in further work, but the
116 main value of the present work is in showing that no proper evidence has ever been presented to
117 reject it.

118

119 II. The last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae

120 (1) Intro

121 The flight status of the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae is the key to understand the
122 evolutionary path of the ratites (the flightless members of the Palaeognathae) and the flying
123 tinamous (the clade of flying members of the Palaeognathae, singular: tinamou). Up until the early
124 2000's, it was assumed that the tinamous formed the sister group to all other Palaeognathae. Based
125 on that assumption, they were used as the outgroup of the ratites in phylogenetic analyses because
126 there was not sufficient computational power to analyse the early DNA datasets without

127 constraining one palaeognath taxon as outgroup (Trevor Worthy, personal communication,
128 6/6/2025). Back then, there was little doubt that the ratites, giant running birds and extinct giant
129 graviportal members of the Palaeognathae, were a monophyletic group and that their last common
130 ancestor was a flightless ratite that had dispersed by means of continental vicariance (Cracraft,
131 1974; Haddrath and Baker, 2012). As the supercontinent Gondwana started breaking apart during
132 the Cretaceous, populations of palaeognath ancestors were split apart, which caused them to
133 genetically and morphologically drift apart from each other to form the species as we know them
134 today. The ratites were once a popular example of continental vicariance, and have even been called
135 'a posterchild for Gondwana vicariance' (Maderspacher, 2017). However, thanks to the analyses of
136 recovered sequences of nuclear DNA (Harshman *et al.*, 2008; Haddrath and Baker, 2012; Almeida *et al.*
137 *et al.*, 2021) and mitochondrial DNA (Phillips *et al.*, 2010; Mitchell *et al.*, 2014) of the recently extinct
138 moa, it became clear that the flying tinamous can no longer be considered a sister group to all
139 ratites. Instead they are deeply nested within the Palaeognathae as sister group to the three families
140 and nine species of moa. Phillips *et al.* (2010) pointed out that this updated phylogenetic tree of the
141 Palaeognathae requires a gain of flight for the tinamou lineage, or multiple losses of flight for the
142 ratite lineages if their last common ancestor was respectively flightless or capable of flight.

143 (2) Dollo's law

144 Philips *et al.* (2010) decided that there exists enough evidence to reject one of the both hypotheses,
145 a flying or a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae. They conducted an ancestral
146 state reconstruction of the flight status of the palaeognath ancestors using maximum likelihood.
147 Their analysis estimated a 98 percent probability that the last common ancestor of the
148 Palaeognathae was a flightless animal, implying that there were no multiple losses of flight for the
149 ratites, but a single origin of flight for the tinamou lineage. However, the authors reasoned that
150 flight loss in birds is much more common and thus much more probable than an origin of flight,
151 something the analysis could not take into account. The percentage they found is thus an
152 overestimation. They further invoked 'Dollo parsimony', a restrictive form of parsimony based on
153 Dollo's law of irreversibility, where complex traits such as flight are not allowed to re-evolve in a
154 lineage where they had been lost previously. The authors concluded that most probably, the last
155 common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a flying bird.

156 However, good reasons exist to doubt this conclusion. First of all, Philips *et al.* (2010) noted that
157 flight loss is a common event, but they failed to mention that continental flight loss is much less
158 common than flight loss on islands, and is even a quite rare event in bird evolution (Mayr, 2016).
159 There is almost no evidence for flight loss in continental Neognathae, or at least not for extant or

160 recently extinct Neognathae for which a DNA-based phylogeny can be constructed. The case of the
161 extinct giant Neognathae is discussed further in this work (section IV subsection 4).

162 Secondly, it seems that the requirements to invoke Dollo's law are not fulfilled. Dollo's law states
163 that complex traits will most probably not evolve back homologously in a lineage where the trait is
164 developmentally lost (Louchart and Viriot, 2011). The palaeognath ancestors of the tinamous surely
165 had wings and feathers at all times, no matter which hypothesis is followed. One can wonder if flight
166 can be considered 'developmentally lost' in a lineage that possesses feathers and well-developed
167 wings. It might be sufficient for a feathered winged ratite to evolve towards a smaller body size, to
168 set in motion the evolutionary path towards flight. A mechanism for this is proposed in section II
169 subsection 6. Furthermore, Philips *et al.* (2010) did not present evidence for the homology of the
170 flight-related traits such as the keel or the pennaceous feathers of the tinamous with those of the
171 Neognathae.

172 Thirdly, Philips *et al.* (2010) did not mention that the evolution from a flying bird towards a ratite
173 body plan encompasses much more than only a flight loss. It would include many evolutionary steps
174 such as loss of keel, loss of patagium, loss of pennaceous feathers and much more (Lowe, 1928).
175 Most of those evolutionary steps are very rare or non-existent in extant or recently-extinct
176 Neognathae of which DNA is available.

177 To conclude, the ancestral state reconstruction of flight (Phillips *et al.*, 2010) seems to not have
178 presented sufficient evidence to reject a flightless last common ancestor for the Palaeognathae.

179 (3) Ancestral substitution rates

180 Contrary to directly assessing the ancestral state of flight, Yonezawa *et al.* (2017) have indirectly
181 inferred the ancestral flight status from ancestral substitution rates. The estimated value of the
182 ancestral substitution rates led the authors to state that the last common ancestor of the
183 Palaeognathae was most probably a flying bird. They reasoned that substitution rates are correlated
184 with body weight and the large flightless birds have substitution rates significantly lower than those
185 of any flying bird. To calculate these ancestral substitution rates, a time calibrated phylogeny was
186 constructed using a relaxed molecular clock method in combination with an MCMC algorithm. The
187 calibration points were based on fossil data, and three different calibration configurations were
188 tested to evaluate the stability of the obtained divergence times. The analysis resulted in rather
189 stable divergence times, which led the authors to the conclusion that they can be considered
190 accurate. The ancestral substitution rates for the stem Palaeognathae had an estimated value of
191 50.3 (substitution/site/billion years), with a 95% highest posterior density (HPD) interval of 35.8-

192 66.0. The terminal branches of the ratites however all had a lower estimated substitution rate, with
193 averages ranging from 8.4 to 27.5. The highest value within a 95 HPD was 32.2, still below 35.8
194 which was the lower limit within a 95 HPD of the stem Palaeognathae. In contrast, flying
195 Neognathae had significantly higher average estimates, ranging from 21.7 for *Gavia pacifica* to 96.9
196 for the songbird *Taeniopygia guttata*. The authors concluded that the substitution rate of the last
197 common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was in the range of substitution rates typically found for
198 flying birds and that they could be expected to have been flying birds as well. Additionally, they
199 made a model with the correlation of substitution rate and body weight, and estimated an ancestral
200 body weight of 1.5 to 2.8 kg for the Palaeognathae assuming random evolution according to a
201 Brownian process. These ancestral birds would thus not have been too heavy to be capable of flight.
202 However, to come to this conclusion, the authors made a plain mistake in their methodology which
203 renders their conclusions meaningless.

204 When looking at the minimum and maximum divergence times chosen in this study, it can
205 immediately be noticed that these are remarkably small intervals. For example, the divergence of
206 the penguins and their sister group was calibrated with a minimum prior of 60 mya and maximum
207 prior of 62 mya, with a reference to Haddrath and Baker (2012). This practice cannot be considered
208 a correct methodology and Yonezawa *et al.* (2017) misinterpreted these ages from the study to
209 which they refer. The supplementary materials of Haddrath and Baker (2012) states that the interval
210 of 60-62 mya can be used as a minimum divergence time of the penguin clade, and not as a
211 maximum. This interval represents an estimation of the age of the oldest penguin fossil, named
212 *Waimanu* (Slack *et al.*, 2006). This means that the penguins are at least 60 million years old, but does
213 not mean they cannot be older than 62 mya. Haddrath and Baker (2012) even explicitly stated that
214 due to the existence of this particular old penguin fossil, they expect the origin of the penguins to
215 have occurred during the late Cretaceous, meaning before 66 mya. Yonezawa *et al.* (2017)
216 committed the same misinterpretation with two other calibration points, namely the divergence
217 between the Jacanidae and their sister group, and the divergence between the Anatidae and the
218 Anseranatidae.

219 In conclusion, this study did not present any evidence against a flightless last common ancestor of
220 the Palaeognathae despite its claims. The practice of using maximum fossil ages as maximum
221 divergence priors is an uncorrect approach which yields unrealistically narrow (and young)
222 divergence intervals. This flaw might be the reason why extremely high outlier values were found for
223 the substitution rates of the tinamous.

224

225 (4) Fossil evidence

226 Some workers might advocate the Lithornithidae as argument in favour of a flying last common
227 ancestor of the running birds. This family of extinct flying birds with a 'palaeognathous palate' from
228 the Paleogene is considered by different authors to belong to the stem Palaeognathae (Widrig,
229 Navalon and Field, 2024). They based this statement on the study of Yonezawa *et al.* (2017). In that
230 study, it is first described how different phylogenetic datasets (Mayr, 2014; Mitchell *et al.*, 2014)
231 have found that the Lithornithidae cluster together with the Tinamidae, deeply nested in the
232 Palaeognathae, and would therefore not be stem palaeognaths. However, Yonezawa *et al.* (2017)
233 made a couple of modifications to the datasets of Houde (1988), Mayr (2014) and Worthy *et al.*
234 (2016), after which they found a basal position of the Lithornithidae, either as stem ostriches or as
235 stem Palaeognathae with a bootstrap value of 92 percent. Their first modification was deleting all
236 characters that showed homoplasy in a reduced dataset containing the taxa from the molecular
237 backbone (the extant taxa plus the elephant bird and the moa). While this approach is useful to limit
238 a dataset to characters that seem stable through evolutionary time, a lot of information may get lost
239 through this procedure. For example for the dataset of Mayr (2014), only 34 characters of the
240 original 243 characters remained, of which 29 had a known character state for *Lithornis*.
241 Additionally, this modification means that most of the remaining characters have a 'primitive'
242 character state for the Palaeognathae and maybe some other basal lineages, and a derived state for
243 the more derived taxa. Numerous derived traits that the Lithornithidae have in common with the
244 tinamous have been removed from the dataset as those often show homoplasy with the
245 Neognathae. As a consequence, the Lithornithids will end up in a very basal position of this
246 phylogeny. This bias is even more problematic because the outgroup in this dataset are the
247 Neognathae, and there is no basal outgroup of non-neornithine Avialae available that allows for an
248 even more basal position than the stem Palaeognathae. If non-neornithine taxa closely related to
249 the Neornithes were included in this study, this analysis may have suggested a non-neornithine
250 position for the Lithornithids. This was already the case for the dataset of Clarke and Chiappe (2001),
251 and the dataset of Livezey and Zusi (2007), even when a molecular backbone is enforced on the
252 Palaeognathae in this latter dataset (Fig S1, additional file 1, section II subsection 8a and additional
253 files 2-5). An additional modification that Yonezawa *et al.* (2017) applied was the removal of 21
254 characters from the dataset of Worthy *et al.* (2016). They were removed because the assumption
255 was made that these missing character states evolved convergently in the ratites and the extinct
256 giant flightless Neognathae, which might be a case of circle reasoning. As shown in section IV
257 subsection (4) of the present work, they may have inherited these character states from their last
258 common ancestor, and removing them from the dataset might have been unjustified.

259 Both modifications could be interpreted as subjective and this study by Yonezawa *et al.* (2017) does
260 not manage to produce convincing evidence that the Lithornithidae were stem Palaeognaths and
261 that the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was therefore a flying bird. The placement of
262 the Lithornithidae is today still subject of reasonable doubt and has varied markedly depending on
263 the author and dataset, mirroring debates about the phylogenetic affinities of Palaeognathae more
264 broadly (Nesbitt and Clarke, 2016). Different datasets suggest they might be stem Neornithes, stem
265 Palaeognathae or stem Tinamidae.

266 5) Evidence from the kiwi and elephant bird

267 Before the tinamous were recognized as sister group to the moa, the ratites were thought to have
268 dispersed by means of Gondwana vicariance and have evolved from a flightless last common
269 ancestor. However, phylogenetic time trees have caused bird paleontologists to reject vicariance in
270 favour of flighted dispersal (Mitchell *et al.*, 2014; Yonezawa *et al.*, 2017; Widrig and Field, 2022). One
271 particular study has claimed to present evidence in favour of a flying last common ancestor of the
272 Palaeognathae. Mitchell *et al.* (2014) formulated this conclusion based on a divergence time study
273 where the age of the last common ancestor of the the kiwi and elephant bird was estimated.

274 After recovering full mitochondrial genomes from the recently extinct elephant bird of Madagascar,
275 the subsequent phylogenetic analysis suggested that most probably, its closest relative was the kiwi
276 from New Zealand (Mitchell *et al.*, 2014). This conclusion was later reaffirmed based on nuclear
277 genes (Grealy *et al.*, 2017). The distribution of the kiwi and elephant bird on their respective islands
278 in combination with estimated divergence times too recent for vicariance has led to the proposal
279 that also these two lineages originated independently from a flying ancestor. Since this study, it is
280 believed that six losses of flight took place in the Palaeognathae (Mitchell *et al.*, 2014) instead of
281 four as proposed by Phillips *et al.* (2010).

282 However, the reasoning of the authors to dismiss the alternative hypothesis is based on the
283 misconception that vicariance can be rejected based on arbitrarily chosen maximum divergence
284 times. Increasingly more recognition has been given to the principle that the age of a clade is often
285 much older than the oldest fossil of that clade (Hedges, 2005). Divergence time studies only
286 calibrated with fossils are useful for all kinds of conclusions concerning minimum divergence times,
287 but cannot present evidence for their maximum divergence priors. Arbitrarily chosen maximum
288 priors cannot produce maximum posteriors that can form evidence against vicariance (Hedges, 2005).

289 Mitchell *et al.* (2014) and subsequent authors who used the assumption that the last common
290 ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a flying bird or that vicariance should be rejected, have failed to

291 mention that it seems very improbable that out of the seven orders of the Palaeognathae, six of
292 them originated by means of a flight loss. In the opinion of the author of the present work, this
293 sixfold 'ratitization' of six out of the seven palaeognath orders, would by far form the most extreme
294 example of convergent evolution among all living organisms. After all, a sixfold flight loss of the
295 Palaeognathae implies as well a sixfold loss of patagium, sixfold loss of keel, sixfold loss of
296 pennaceous feathers, sixfold loss of filoplumes, sixfold loss of plumules, five to sixfold gigantism and
297 more (Lowe, 1928), a most remarkable observation that seems never mentioned in the literature.

298 Regardless of these flight-related traits, Mitchell *et al.* (2014) did not back this hypothesis with an
299 ancestral state reconstruction of flight itself. In the present work, a new ancestral state
300 reconstruction of flight was conducted using maximum likelihood in the software Mesquite
301 (Maddison and Maddison, 2023) on the phylogenetic tree from Mitchell *et al.* (2014), see additional
302 file 6. The similarity to the analysis by Phillips *et al.* (2010) is evident when comparing their resulting
303 0.98 percent probability of a flightless ancestor of the Palaeognathae, with the result of 0.987 in the
304 present analysis. This slightly higher value can be attributed to the outgroup, which in this case
305 consists of flightless crocodylian taxa. It is most often assumed that the Palaeognathae originated
306 from flying birds, as is suggested by their phylogenetic relation to flying fossil taxa (Fig. S1, additional
307 file 1), so the ancestral state reconstruction was repeated but with the two outgroup taxa modified
308 to a flying status in order to represent the flying non-neornithine birds (Fig. 1). After this
309 modification, the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae had an estimated probability of 0.982
310 of being flightless, which is even closer to the value estimated by Phillips *et al.* (2010).

311 In both the unmodified and modified analysis, the calculated probabilities seem to suggest a
312 flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae as was the case in the study of Phillips *et al.*
313 (2010). However, the proposed sixfold flight loss with a flying last common ancestor of the kiwi
314 (*Apteryx*) and the elephant bird (*Mullerornis* and *Aepyornis*) by Mitchell *et al.* (2014) calls for an
315 ancestral state reconstruction of flight for this precise ancestor. The probability that this ancestor
316 was flightless has in the present analysis an estimated value of 0.99997 in the situation of a flightless
317 outgroup, and 0.99996 in the case of a modified flying outgroup (Fig. 1). These values do not change
318 significantly when a molecular backbone of the Palaeognathae with different positions of the
319 rheidae is applied based on results from Stiller *et al.* (2024), see additional files 4 and 5. Based on
320 this result, and based on the assessment that their argument to reject a flightless ancestor is based
321 on a misconception, the hypothesis of Mitchell *et al.* (2014) of a flying last common ancestor of the
322 elephant bird and kiwi can be rejected. Furthermore, that means that the ancestral state of the kiwi

323 and elephant bird no longer represents evidence in favour of rejecting a flightless last common
324 ancestor of the Palaeognathae.

325 The last common ancestor of the kiwi and elephant bird was most probably a flightless ratite. If that
326 was indeed the case, this ancestor had to disperse over land by Gondwana vicariance in order for
327 their descendants to reach Madagascar and New Zealand. This requires a much older origin than has
328 been estimated before. This older origin may seem in disagreement with multiple time calibration
329 studies, which was the reason why Mitchell *et al.* (2014) rejected this possibility. But as pointed out
330 by Heads (2005), fossil-based time calibration studies cannot present any evidence for their
331 arbitrarily chosen maximum divergence times, and such studies can therefore not deliver evidence
332 to reject continental vicariance.

333
334 **Fig. 1** Ancestral state reconstruction of flight on a phylogenetic tree from Mitchell *et al.* (2014) with
335 a modified flight status for the outgroup. The probabilities of being flightless have an estimated
336 value of 0.982 for the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae, and 0.99996 for the last common

337 ancestor of the kiwi (*Apteryx*) and the elephant birds (*Aepyornis* and *Mullerornis*). Flying taxa and
338 the modified outgroup are indicated with black, the flightless Palaeognathae and the penguin
339 *Pygoscelis* are indicated with white. This result strongly suggests that the view of Mitchell *et al.*
340 (2014) of flighted dispersal of the kiwi and elephant bird lineage can be rejected. Additionally, the
341 ancestral state of the kiwi and elephant bird does no longer present any evidence in favour of
342 rejecting a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae.

343

344 If the kiwi and elephant bird lineages originated through continental vicariance, they originated at
345 the moment that Madagascar and New Zealand were no longer connected by land. The time of
346 isolation is controversial for both land masses. The start of the continental breakup between
347 Zealandia and Gondwana has been estimated around 82 mya (Cooper *et al.*, 2001) or 83 mya
348 (Strogen *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, it is generally believed that the final continental separation of
349 Zealandia with Australia took place around 62 Mya (Strogen *et al.*, 2022; Gaina *et al.*, 1999).
350 However, both dates don't necessarily give information on the biological isolation of land-dwelling
351 fauna on the island, which could have been much earlier than the final continental separation, as
352 this could have taken place under water. However, the exact date of biological separation of New
353 Zealand doesn't seem to matter here. If New Zealand was ecologically isolated after the Cretaceous
354 period, the separation of New Zealand and Madagascar will be determined by the time of isolation
355 of Madagascar from Gondwana. Mitchell *et al.* (2014) stated that Madagascar was disconnected
356 from Gondwana before 100 mya. But there exist different hypotheses in favour of one or more land
357 bridges between Indo-Madagascar and the Antarctica/Australia/South-America landmass until the
358 late Cretaceous (Noonan and Chippendale, 2006) either by means of the Kerguelen plateau (Hay *et al.*,
359 1999) or by the Gunnerus Ridge (Case, 2002; Case and Kranan, 2002). Ali and Krause (2011)
360 stated that no convincing evidence exists for the Gunnerus ridge as a biological connection of
361 Madagascar to Gondwana during the late Cretaceous. They suggest that Indo-Madagascar was
362 isolated before the end of the early Cretaceous, meaning before 100 Mya. If one of these land
363 bridges was present, it could be considered that the kiwi and elephant bird lineages diverged in the
364 late Cretaceous, and if not, they had to diverge before the end of the early Cretaceous. In both cases
365 and when vicariance is assumed, this would mean that geological data suggests that both the kiwi
366 and elephant bird lineages survived the K-P extinction event, and as flightless animals.

367 There are currently two opposing hypotheses on the evolution of the kiwi and the above evidence
368 strongly favours one of them. Firstly, there is the hypothesis that the kiwi are phyletic dwarves and
369 had a giant ancestor. They possess a remarkably large egg, having the largest egg to body weight

370 ratio of all birds. The female carries an egg so large, that during the last days of her pregnancy her
371 stomach is flattened, preventing her from taking up food (Gould, 1986). It has been reasoned that
372 this massive egg was probably the remnant of a giant ratite ancestor of the kiwi (Calder, 1978;
373 Gould, 1986). This hypothesis has been challenged by authors who described the oldest fossil kiwi,
374 *Proapteryx* from the Miocene of St Bathans, New Zealand (Worthy *et al.*, 2013). Because the
375 estimated body weight of this extinct kiwi, around 234 g, was much smaller than any extant kiwi, the
376 authors reasoned that it may have been capable of flight, and that possibly, the kiwi evolved from a
377 small flying ancestor. Furthermore, they reasoned that it is unlikely that other larger kiwi were
378 around on New Zealand, as about 5000 fossil non-kiwi birds are known from the St Bathans fauna,
379 implying that it is unlikely that any undiscovered bird species had occurred at that particular locality,
380 and possibly on the whole island, at that particular time.

381 Aside from the minor remark that the authors did not explicitly state why they are certain that both
382 *Proapteryx* fossils belonged to fully adult specimens, there are good reasons to doubt if this fossil is
383 any evidence strong enough to reject a flightless last common ancestor of the kiwi and elephant
384 bird. Most importantly, the authors were not able to show fossil evidence that this small kiwi had
385 any adaptations to flight, such as a keel. Furthermore, the body weight of the extant kiwi is not the
386 reason why they cannot fly; their weight is well within the range of flying birds and thus the finding
387 of an even smaller kiwi is thus no evidence that it was capable of flight. Also, the scarcity of kiwi
388 fossils does not prove at all that no other (larger) kiwi were around at that time. After all, divergence
389 time estimates (Stiller *et al.*, 2024) show that kiwi must have been around much earlier than the
390 Miocene period, and the lack of older kiwi fossils already suggests that their fossil record is highly
391 fragmentary. Furthermore, the assessment that probably no undiscovered kiwi species existed in a
392 sampled area where 5000 fossil birds were found (or in all of New Zealand) is a flawed comparison.
393 Many birds are known to show flocking behaviour or have high population densities, but the kiwi
394 happens to be a highly solitary animal with large territories (Keye *et al.*, 2011). They could also have
395 been more abundant in other localities than in this particular one. The existence of a small kiwi on
396 New Zealand during the Miocene is not convincing evidence to reject the hypothesis defended by
397 Calder (1978) and Gould (1986). Their views of a giant kiwi ancestor do seem supported by the
398 finding of a sister relation of the kiwi and the elephant bird (Mitchell *et al.*, 2014). It would seem like
399 an incredible coincidence that the kiwi, with the largest egg/body mass ratio, happens to be the
400 sister taxon of the heaviest bird that ever lived, convergently attaining extremely large egg sizes
401 from a small ancestor, but only one of them attaining a giant body size. On top of that, their
402 supposed flying relatives went extinct and did not leave us with any fossil evidence of their
403 existence. That is so much to assume, that the conservative hypothesis of a flightless last common

404 ancestor hardly seems challenged by the finding of a small kiwi fossil, until strong evidence would
405 prove the contrary.

406 If the scientific community agrees with the assessment that there is no evidence available to reject
407 the results of this ancestral state reconstruction (Fig. 1) and to reject continental vicariance for the
408 kiwi and elephant bird, they should consider the more conservative and parsimonious hypothesis.
409 With a flightless last common ancestor of the kiwi and elephant bird, the (Cretaceous) divergence
410 based on continental vicariance of both taxa should be treated as a calibration point in future time
411 calibration studies. This could form a rare way if not the only way of introducing a calibration point
412 (instead of an interval) and thus a real maximum divergence prior into the phylogeny of the
413 Neornithes. As a consequence, the posterior divergence times within the Palaeognathae but also
414 Neognathae will probably turn out to be older than has been estimated before.

415 6) The flight of the tinamou

416 The existence of the tinamous as flying members of the Palaeognathae seems to be largely
417 responsible for the widespread belief that the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a
418 flying bird. If that ancestor were flightless, an origin of flight would be required in the tinamou
419 lineage, independent of the origin of flight of the other birds. This has been considered unlikely, as
420 acquiring flight is thought to be a rare step in evolution (Phillips *et al.*, 2010). However the flight
421 skills and morphology of the tinamou must be taken into account.

422 The tinamous must be about the worst at flying among all flying birds. They lack a functional
423 pygostyle and tail, which causes problems with steering, and they have been known to crash into
424 houses, branches, wires and posts, sometimes leading to their death (Cabot, 1992). Relative to their
425 body size, they have the smallest hearts of all flying birds, which in combination with their small
426 lungs and wings is thought to cause their lack of stamina when flying. Their flight is indeed restricted
427 to short bursts, which can only be performed two or three consecutive times before they are so
428 exhausted that it is possible to hand-catch them (Cabot, 1992). This type of flight has even been
429 called non-sustained flapping flight (Altimiras *et al.*, 2017), meaning there is a (semantic) debate if
430 the tinamous are even capable of sustained flight. If flight originated in the tinamou lineage, they do
431 not deserve equal praise for this accomplishment as do the Neognathae, as they are barely, if at all
432 capable of sustained flight. If anything, their lackluster flight skills could be interpreted as evidence
433 for an independent origin of flight. It is hard to imagine that their ancestor possessed better flight
434 skills, had a larger heart, larger lungs and a better functioning tail and would be capable of long-
435 distance dispersal by flight. It would have to be assumed that at some point in evolution, these traits

436 degenerated despite living on a continent where the selection pressures caused by predation (unlike
437 on some islands or continental islands) surely and continuously favoured flight optimization.

438 The alternative would be an origin of flight in the tinamou lineage. Much has been written about the
439 origin of flight in birds from a non-bird dinosaur ancestor. The two most popular hypotheses are
440 'from the trees down' and 'from the ground up'. The latter one suggests that flight arose in lineages
441 of fast-running winged dinosaurs, which used flapping of their wings to create more thrust and
442 enable faster running (Ostrom, 1979), which seems like a simplistic and insufficient explanation for a
443 gradual evolution of flight. However, one particular and less-discussed hypothesis on the origin of
444 flight seems strikingly applicable to the tinamou lineage. Many birds, the tinamous included, are
445 known to display a behaviour that has been called 'wing assisted inclined running' or WAIR (Dial,
446 2003; Heers, Dial and Tobalske, 2014). When these birds and even their flightless chicks are running
447 up on an inclined surface, they flap their wings. By using this technique, they can even climb
448 vertically, enabling them to run from the ground up into a tree. Afterwards, they jump down to the
449 forest floor, again while flapping their wings to have a softer landing. In the context of fleeing from a
450 predator, WAIR allows both chicks and adults to find safety on higher grounds. The WAIR behaviour
451 observed in flightless chicks has been proposed as a mechanism how flight originated in flightless
452 winged dinosaurs (Heers, Dial and Tobalske, 2014). Similarly, the tinamou ancestor could have been
453 a flightless giant Palaeognath, which acquired a smaller body size in a forested habitat. After
454 perfecting its WAIR technique to flee from predators, which the modern tinamous still use today,
455 their ancestral lineage may have acquired enough adaptations such as a keelbone to make short
456 flights possible.

457 There might even be fossil evidence of the role of WAIR or other locomotion-related selection
458 pressures in a possible origin of flight in ground-dwelling feathered dinosaurs. It has been well
459 established that the fossil oviraptorosaur *Caudipteryx* possessed symmetrical flight feathers, while it
460 is not believed to have been capable of flight, nor is it thought to have evolved from a flying ancestor
461 (Qiang *et al.*, 1998). This find is a most remarkable discovery and suggests that this taxon was
462 evolving under similar selection pressures that could lead to the origin of flight. It is hard to imagine
463 that evolution has led to the origin of pennaceous flight feathers, if this animal did not use its wings
464 for locomotion in a similar way as in flying birds. For *Caudipteryx* specifically, it has been proposed
465 that WAIR might have been the mechanism by which its flight-related adaptations evolved (Dial,
466 2003). Another option is that *Caudipteryx* possibly benefitted from improved manoeuvrability thanks
467 to its wings with pennaceous feathers, for example when performing sharp turns and breaking
468 (Talori *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, Zhao *et al.* (2022) presented evidence from kinematics and

469 dynamics tested on a *Caudipteryx* robot that suggests that wing flapping aiding in locomotion
470 originated before the origin of flight. Whether by means of WAIR or by means of other
471 functionalities related to locomotion, *Caudipteryx* illustrates that ‘from the ground up’ is a perfectly
472 viable hypothesis for an origin of flight, and illustrates how ratites could perfectly evolve towards
473 small ground-dwelling winged Palaeognathae with pennaceous feathers, not very different from the
474 tinamous, which barely possess more adaptations to flight than *Caudipteryx*.

475 Some workers might oppose to the idea that a keel could evolve multiple times independently from
476 each other. Indeed, there is not much evidence that the keel has originated multiple times, except
477 for once in birds, and maybe a keel-like structure in the flying pterosaurs (Hone, 2023). However, a
478 parallel could be made to a similar structure, of which ample evidence suggests it has originated
479 many times, namely the sagittal crest. This structure, which is a ridge formed by an extension of
480 bones of the skull, serves as anchor point of the jaw muscles in many animals. It can be seen in the
481 skull of hyena’s, some hominids, wolves, giant panda’s and tapirs (DeSantis *et al.*, 2020), badgers,
482 *Tyrannosaurus* and more. Just like the keel, it is not a completely novel structure, but merely an
483 extension from existing bone. It seems to occur in animals with an exceptionally large bite force.
484 One could state that when selection pressures favour immense biting forces, the sagittal crest will
485 have a relatively high probability of originating by the process of evolution. The same might be true
486 for a keel in feathered winged dinosaurs exposed to selection pressures that would favor flight.

487 One last remarkable aspect of the tinamous must be mentioned. All flying and flightless Neognathae
488 possess pennaceous feathers for flight, where the barbules of the pennaceous feathers are attached
489 to each other by means of little hooks present on the distal barbules, locking into the proximal
490 barbules. In the tinamous however, there is a solid secondary fusion of the proximal barbules into a
491 bar-like structure to which the hooks present on the distal barbules attach (Chandler, 1916). The
492 barbules are thus more effectively attached to each other than in any other bird. Even though this
493 fundamental difference in attachment mechanism between the tinamous and the Neognathae, this
494 does not imply that their flight feathers are non-homologous. On the other hand however, it seems
495 an incredible coincidence that precisely and only in the tinamous, this perfected barbule attachment
496 has originated from an ancestral feather that was more similar to the ones of the Neognathae. A
497 possible non-homology between the flight feathers of the tinamous and the Neognathae should be
498 further investigated. If this could be confirmed, it would imply a non-homology of flight and thus a
499 ratite ancestor of the tinamous.

500 In short, the capacity of modern tinamous to perform a simple version of flight is not necessarily a
501 near-impossible accomplishment, neither is it a strong argument for a flying last common ancestor

502 of the Palaeognathae. For animals with the right body size and equipped with wings and feathers,
503 maybe an origin of flight is not an improbable evolutionary step at all.

504

505 (7) *Diogenornis*, a missing link?

506 Fossil evidence might exist of the hypothesis that is defended here. If the last common ancestor of
507 the Palaeognathae was a flightless ratite, that means that the stem Tinamidae went through an
508 evolutionary step of flight origin. In that case, the existence of a small ratite with well-developed
509 wings and similarities with the tinamou could be expected to have existed. Interestingly, there is one
510 fossil taxon that seems to fit this description rather well, but may have been overlooked as possible
511 stem tinamou because of the assumption that tinamous never had a ratite ancestor. This fossil taxon
512 is known as *Diogenornis*, the oldest named fossil that has uncontroversially been recognized as a
513 ratite (Widrig and Field, 2022). This taxon is only known from South-America, the same continent on
514 which the tinamous occur. The type material was uncovered in Itaboraí, Brazil, with a debated age of
515 early Eocene or middle-late Paleocene. However, more material was referred to *Diogenornis* from
516 even older layers in the Rio Chico formation of Argentina, namely from middle Paleocene (Widrig
517 and Field, 2022), thus around 60 million years ago. That means that *Diogenornis* occurred as a
518 flightless ratite almost right after the extinction of the land dinosaurs. Its phylogenetic relations
519 remain obscure, and no phylogenetic analyses that include a molecular backbone could be found. It
520 has been described as a relative to the rhea lineage (Alvarenga, 1983), but it has also been suggested
521 to have closer affinities to the casuariids (Alvarenga, 2010). Currently it is often treated as a rhea
522 relative (Agnolin, 2017; Widrig and Field, 2022).

523 *Diogenornis* was a relatively small ratite, smaller than a rhea and with larger wings, a larger humerus
524 than the rhea and a rather large proximal phalanx of the second digit. Under the assumption that
525 the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a flying bird, these traits have been interpreted
526 as evidence for its close relation to this flying ancestor. However, under the hypothesis presented in
527 this work, it could be that *Diogenornis* is a missing link ratite with already adaptations to WAIR and
528 ultimately towards flight, and could be a stem member of the Tinamidae. In the light of this
529 hypothesis, it might be interesting to note that Alvarenga (1983) described that *Diogenornis* not only
530 has similarities to the rhea's, but also some to the Tinamidae. *Diogenornis* had a much more narrow
531 beak than the rhea, which it has in common with the cassowaries and the Tinamidae. Furthermore,
532 Alvarenga (1983) noted on the tibiotarsi of *Diogenornis* that the endocondyle is narrower and
533 projects more posteriorly than in rhea, being separated from the ectocondyle by a more evident
534 groove, in which it resembles the Tinamidae. Additionally, the proximal head of the humerus is

535 rounded, and the diaphysis is elliptical in cross-section, similar to that of the Tinamidae and contrary
536 to the triangular head and cross-section in the rhea. A proper phylogenetic study with molecular
537 backbone might form extra evidence for this hypothesis in future work. Given its similarities to
538 rhea's and also Tinamidae, it seems not unthinkable that a phylogenetic analysis will retrieve it as a
539 stem member of the Tinamidae, as a missing link between the running birds and the tinamous. That
540 could be a parsimonious hypothesis, in the sense that none of its similarities to the ratites and its
541 similarities to the tinamous would have to be homoplasies, meaning that no convergent evolution
542 would be required.

543 8) Miscellaneous indications in favour of a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae
544 Some additional arguments are added (additional file 1, section II subsection 8) that might form
545 support for a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae. These indications come from
546 the branch lengths of the stem Palaeognathae and stem Neognathae in phylogenetic trees, from the
547 distribution of the pygostyle in the Neornithes, and from the 'living fossil phenomenon'. It is
548 emphasized again that none of these arguments are meant to form conclusive evidence in favour of
549 a flightless last common ancestor. This work merely shows that no convincing evidence exists to
550 reject a flightless LCA, and that many aspects about palaeognath evolution make more sense in the
551 light of a flightless last common ancestor.

552 9) Conclusion

553 Philips *et al.* (2010), Mitchell *et al.* (2014) and Yonezawa *et al.* (2017) all have claimed to present
554 different evidence from which a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae can be
555 rejected. However, it was shown here that their methods are flawed and did not provide evidence to
556 reject a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae. Dollo's law seems not applicable for
557 different reasons, fossil-based time calibrations can never form evidence against vicariance (Heads,
558 2005) and substitution rates cannot be a reliable argument when they are derived from divergence
559 times that were incorrectly estimated by taking fossil ages as maximum divergence times. In the
560 present study, an ancestral state reconstruction was conducted to show how improbable the
561 currently accepted hypothesis on the evolution of Palaeognathae is, including its sixfold flight loss. It
562 was shown that most probably, the last common ancestor of the kiwi and elephant bird was not a
563 flying bird and could not disperse by flight. Furthermore, it is shown that the last common ancestor
564 of the Palaeognathae was probably a flightless animal. This not only the most parsimonious and
565 likely hypothesis for flight in the Palaeognathae, but also for the keel, for pennaceous feathers and
566 other traits related to flight (Lowe, 1928). It is hypothesized that if the tinamous are indeed nested
567 within the flightless Palaeognathae, the tinamou lineage would have acquired flight independent

568 from the other birds by means of wing assisted inclined running, a behaviour still displayed by the
569 extant tinamous.

570 No evidence seems to exist in favour of a flying last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae, and no
571 evidence has been presented for the existence of flying stem ostriches, flying stem kiwi, flying New
572 Zealand stem moa, flying stem casuariforms, flying stem rhea's and flying stem elephant birds. That
573 means that a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae will remain the conservative
574 hypothesis supported by likelihood and parsimony, until convincing evidence is found to reject this.

575

576 III. Consequences: Pandora's box

577 This work has so far shown that an alternative hypothesis on the evolution of the Palaeognathae
578 must be considered. Some readers will even agree that convincing evidence was presented to reject
579 a flying last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae from the principles of parsimony and results
580 from ancestral state reconstructions. A flightless last common ancestor should thus be treated as a
581 likely, conservative hypothesis which seemingly cannot be rejected at present by any convincing
582 evidence. Furthermore, it was shown with rather convincing evidence, that most probably the last
583 common ancestor of the kiwi and elephant bird was a flightless bird. It probably dispersed by means
584 of Gondwana vicariance and the kiwi and elephant bird probably originated much earlier than has
585 been estimated. The consequences of the findings presented here are far-reaching and open the box
586 of Pandora for the understanding of the evolution of Palaeognathae the origin of the extant birds or
587 Neornithes.

588 First of all, a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae would have a large impact on our
589 understanding of the dispersal of the Palaeognathae to their current geographical range. The
590 continental vicariance hypothesis would have to be restored to explain the presence of the flightless
591 ratites on their islands, which they had to reach by foot and not by air.

592 Secondly, aside from the kiwi and elephant bird lineages, the other Palaeognathae orders also had
593 to originate much earlier than estimated, and at least four lineages before the end of the
594 Cretaceous. Furthermore, with those new calibration points from continental vicariance that provide
595 a real way to estimate a maximum divergence, the current divergence times within the Neognathae
596 may be proven underestimations as well.

597 Thirdly, if the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was not a flying bird, the most direct
598 evidence that the (stem) Palaeognathae at some point originated from flying birds would no longer

599 be applicable. On top of that, all events of flight loss and gigantism in the crown Palaeognathae
600 would not seem to have taken place, reducing evidence for this 'ratitization', which still supposedly
601 took place in the stem Palaeognathae. This allows for the question to be asked: "Are Palaeognathae
602 birds?" As basal clade of the Neornithes, it is possible that they are a lineage of non-bird dinosaur
603 that never went through a flight phase nor a flight loss and gigantism, but just remained with their
604 large non-bird dinosaur body. This idea has been suggested before by different authors (Lowe,
605 1928a; Lowe, 1935; Friant, 1968; Barsbold, 1983) but their arguments have lately been neglected.
606 This is partially because they are not congruent with modern morphology-based phylogenetic trees,
607 but more importantly also based on the assumption that the last common ancestor of the
608 Palaeognathae was a flying bird, which is shown here to be probably incorrect. This begs for the
609 question: Is enough evidence from morphology-based methods available to confidently reject a
610 flightless non-bird origin of the Palaeognathae?

611 Fourthly, if the Neognathae and the Palaeognathae existed much earlier than previously believed,
612 the 'rocks versus clocks' discrepancy gets even bigger. This enigma describes the large gap between
613 the oldest fossils of the Neornithes, Neognathae and Palaeognathae ('rocks') and their much earlier
614 origin as estimated by molecular clock methods ('clocks').

615 Fifthly, it has been assumed that the multifold ratitization took place after the extinction of the land
616 dinosaurs. They would have taken up the ecological niche of the 'ostrich mimic dinosaurs'
617 (Ornithomimosauridae) and dinosaurs alike, which were extinct by then. However, if the last
618 common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was flightless, and if they were walking earth earlier than
619 the late-Cretaceous disconnection of Madagascar and New Zealand (see section II, subsection 5),
620 that means that ostrich-like ancestors of the Palaeognathae coexisted on earth with the land
621 dinosaurs such as the ostrich mimic dinosaur. Island gigantism or the absence of large predator
622 dinosaurs are no longer applicable to explain this gigantism from a flying bird, because the stem
623 Palaeognathae evolved on Gondwana in the presence of predatory dinosaurs. An explanation would
624 be required for how a small flying bird would have evolved towards a giant runner body plan on a
625 continent, giving rise to the ratites in the presence of non-bird dinosaurs.

626

627 IV. The origin of the Palaeognathae

628 Did the Palaeognathae evolve from flying ancestors, or are they non-bird dinosaurs? Aside from a
629 handful of relatively old studies (Lowe, 1928a; Lowe, 1935; Friant, 1968; Barsbold, 1983), there
630 seems nowadays a general agreement that sufficient evidence exists for the hypothesis that

631 Palaeognathae originated from flying birds. Even if there is no longer strong evidence from the flight
632 status of their last common ancestor, there still remains other evidence that points into this
633 direction. This evidence is here critically reviewed. Furthermore, evidence that would support a non-
634 bird origin of the Palaeognathae is discussed.

635

636 (1) Evidence from morphology-based phylogenies

637 (a) Intro

638 In morphology-based phylogenetic analyses that include Palaeognathae, Neognathae and extinct
639 Mesozoic flying birds, the clade of the Neornithes consisting of the Palaeognathae and Neognathae
640 always appear to be sister clades nested within a larger clade containing those extinct flying
641 dinosaurs (Fig. S1, additional file 1). The fact that the Neornithes seem to nest within these flying
642 taxa clearly suggests that the ancestor of the Neornithes and thus the ancestor of the Palaeognathae
643 was a flying bird. Note that from now on term 'Mesozoic birds' is here avoided, because the present
644 work questions the origin of the Palaeognathae or even the Neornithes as a whole, as they may be
645 less related to other flying dinosaurs than thought. If the modern birds evolved from a different
646 origin of flight than the Mesozoic flying dinosaurs, these fossil non-neornithine taxa cannot be called
647 birds anymore, and taxonomic names such as 'Avialae' will have to be revised.

648 Sometimes a phylogenetic hypothesis with a high consistency index can mislead scientists for years.
649 Since the availability of large genomic datasets, it has become increasingly clear that incongruence
650 between phylogenies based on morphology and molecular data is frequently the norm rather than
651 the exception (Waddell *et al.*, 1999; Jeffroy *et al.*, 2006; Rodríguez-Ezpeleta *et al.*, 2007, Dávalos *et*
652 *al.*, 2012). Mismatches between evolutionary processes and phylogenetic models can lead to high
653 confidence in incorrect hypotheses (Dávalos *et al.*, 2012). Different phenomena have been described
654 that might systematically cause misguided phylogenetic hypotheses based on morphological data,
655 such as convergent evolution (Hedges and Sibley, 1994; McCracken *et al.*, 1999; Wiens, Chippindale
656 and Hillis, 2003), functional and developmental character linkage (Keating, Garwood and Sansom,
657 2023), long branch attraction (Bergsten, 2005), stemward slippage (Sansom and Wills, 2013), missing
658 data (Donoghue *et al.*, 1989; Huelsenbeck, 1991) and researcher bias concerning character coding or
659 taxon choice (Estabrook *et al.* 1975; Hennig, 1966; Wagner, 2000). Regardless of the mechanism, it is
660 generally agreed by biologists that even consistently found morphology-based phylogenies do not
661 necessarily represent the correct evolutionary relations.

662 (b) Biased taxon choice

663 In the present work, it is suggested that the Palaeognathae might have not originated from a flying
664 lineage, and are thus non-bird dinosaurs. If morphological evidence for or against this hypothesis is
665 to be explored, one would want to conduct a phylogenetic study that includes both ratites and flying
666 taxa, but also feathered winged flightless dinosaurs that have some similarities with the ratites such
667 as flightless non-neornithine Avialae or even a selection of flightless non-Avialae. Interestingly, some
668 fossil taxa do match with this description, but no morphological studies were found where they were
669 analysed together with ratites. It is thus possible that a researcher bias is at play where specific taxa
670 are not recognized as potential relatives to certain other taxa (Wagner, 2000), in this case the ratites
671 and potential relatives. The reason for the systematic exclusion of ratites or their potential relatives
672 from phylogenetic studies may be the general belief that the last common ancestor of the
673 Palaeognathae was a flying bird. However, the present work has already shown that this is probably
674 not correct, or at least that no credible evidence exists to reject a flightless ancestor. As such, these
675 flightless candidate stem Palaeognathae or candidate stem Neornithes should be included in
676 phylogenetic studies about the origin of the Palaeognathae, and the origin of the Neornithes.

677 The first example is *Patagopteryx*. This 'flightless bird' from 85 mya, Argentina, has been originally
678 described by Alvarenga and Bonaparte (1992) as the oldest ratite fossil, living way before the land
679 dinosaurs went extinct. This would turn *Patagopteryx* in an extraordinary find, because no ratites
680 were known from the Cretaceous. However, their view was opposed by Chiappe (1991) even before
681 the original description was published. It was argued by Chiappe (1991) that *Patagopteryx* has some
682 traits that are primitive compared to the Neornithes, suggesting a more basal position within the
683 Avialae instead. *Patagopteryx* would have acquired flightlessness independently from any other
684 known flightless bird. Alvarenga (1993) disagreed with this view, repeating arguments for ratite
685 affinities of *Patagopteryx*. The hypothesis of ratite affinities of *Patagopteryx* was also supported by
686 Kurochkin (1995), who summed up nine characters that ratites and *Patagopteryx* seem to have in
687 common and would show their relatedness. Later, Chiappe (1995) settled the issue by conducting a
688 phylogenetic analysis based on 73 morphological characters. *Patagopteryx* was retrieved as a basal
689 avialan and not as a neornithine. However, no ratite taxa were included in this study, and the
690 modern birds were represented by one taxon called 'Neornithes'. No more recent morphological
691 studies could be found that included both *Patagopteryx* and at least one ratite. In contrast, plenty of
692 studies were found in which *Patagopteryx* is included and where either no Palaeognathae are
693 included, or the Palaeognathae are represented only by a flying tinamou (Cau *et al.*, 2015; Cau *et al.*,
694 2017; Chatterjee, 1999; Clarke and Middleton, 2008; Gao *et al.*, 2008; Hu, O'Connor and Zhou, 2015;
695 Huang *et al.*, 2016; Imai *et al.*, 2019; Kurochkin *et al.*, 2011; Li *et al.*, 2014; Longrich, Tokaryk and
696 Field, 2011; OConnor and Zelenkov, 2013; OConnor *et al.*, 2009; OConnor, Chiappe and Bell, 2011;

697 OConnor, Averianov and Zelenkov; 2014, Wang and Liu, 2016; Wang and Zhou, 2019). This is
698 understandable for studies that took place before the tinamous were rejected as basal
699 Palaeognaths. But since it is well established that the ostrich clade and not the tinamou clade forms
700 the sister clade to all other Palaeognathae, it can no longer be defended to represent the
701 Palaeognathae with only a tinamou. This shows that the assumption of a flying last common
702 ancestor of the Palaeognathae may have consequences even for phylogenetic analyses on extinct
703 flying and flightless dinosaurs (mainly, but not limited to the avialans). As ratites and *Patagopteryx*
704 have not been analysed together yet in a phylogenetic study, no attempts have really been made to
705 dismiss the argumentation of Kurochkin (1995) in favour of ratite affinities for *Patagopteryx*. This
706 fossil taxon should thus still be considered a candidate stem ratite. The unifying hypothesis
707 presented in this work (section V, subsection 2), even offers a framework in which both seemingly
708 opposing views could be correct, and the primitivity of *Patagopteryx* compared to all of the extant
709 Neornithes would make perfect sense.

710 The second example is *Gargantuavis*. This large flightless taxon is known from the late Cretaceous in
711 France and Spain (Buffetaut *et al.*, 2019), and possibly Romania (Mayr *et al.*, 2020). Although its
712 fossil record is highly incomplete, the remains are thought to belong to a secondarily flightless bird
713 with the size of an ostrich, but it seems currently believed that is not directly related to the ratites. It
714 has been considered a basal member of the Ornithurae (Buffetaut and Angst, 2020), a clade that
715 includes all Neornithes and the fossil taxa *Apsaravis*, *Ichthyornis* and the Hesperornithes, but
716 excluding the Enantiornithes (Gauthier and de Queiroz, 2001). Only one phylogenetic analysis could
717 be found in which *Gargantuavis* was included (Cau, 2024). This study suggests that *Gargantuavis*
718 was a secondarily flightless member of the Enantiornithes, a diverse clade of flying Mesozoic
719 avialans. This hypothesis however is not supported by convincing evidence. Firstly, only a few
720 morphological characters from *Gargantuavis* were included in the study, namely those related to the
721 incomplete pelvis described by Buffetaut and Le Loeuff (1998). The more recently found characters
722 from a cervical vertebra (Buffetaut and Angst, 2012) and a femur (Buffetaut *et al.*, 2019) were not
723 included. Secondly, the yet undescribed scapulae that are thought to have belonged to *Gargantuavis*
724 disagree with an identification as Enantiornithine (E. Buffetaut, personal communication,
725 14/09/2024), which are known to have highly characteristic scapulae. Thirdly, no ratites were
726 included in this study, which means the same bias may be at play as in the case of *Patagopteryx*.
727 Until more morphological evidence emerges, its affinities remain unclear. *Gargantuavis* might as
728 well represent a stem palaeognath and should be included in studies on the origin of modern birds.
729 Again as with *Patagopteryx*, the unifying hypothesis presented in this work (section V, subsection 2)
730 could offer a framework in which *Gargantuavis* shares its similarities with the Palaeognathae by

731 common descent, but at the same time *Gargantuavis* remains in a primitive position compared to all
732 extant Neornithes.

733 The third example is the enigmatic *Avimimus*. This fossil bipedal dinosaur was described by Kurzanov
734 (1981), who highlighted the incredible similarities between this dinosaur and the modern birds
735 (Kurzanov 1987). He argued that *Avimimus* has more in common with birds than *Archaeopteryx* has.
736 Some of the characters it has in common with the birds could be considered key bird characters,
737 such as the presence of a tibiotarsus, reduced tail, carpometacarpus, tarsometatarsus, synsacrum,
738 beak with rhamphotheca and reduced teeth, all of which are indeed absent in *Archaeopteryx* as
739 pointed out by Ostrom (1979). Most morphological studies place *Avimimus* in the Oviraptorosauria,
740 further related from the modern birds than *Archaeopteryx*. However, one single study (Maryanska,
741 Osmolska and Wolsan, 2002) based on 195 characters retrieved a sister relation between *Avimimus*
742 and *Confuciusornis* (a Mesozoic bird that is thought to be more derived than *Archaeopteryx*) to the
743 exclusion of *Archaeopteryx*. The authors considered that *Avimimus* might be a secondarily flightless
744 bird just like the ratites, but evolved independently from them. Another option would of course be
745 that *Archaeopteryx* is less related to the Avialae than previously thought, and represents an
746 independent ornithized lineage as proposed by Thulborn (1984). In the context of a flightless last
747 common ancestor of the Palaeognathae, it would be interesting to conduct a study including both
748 *Avimimus* and ratites, however, no study was found where *Avimimus* and ratites were in the same
749 dataset. This might be a case of bias, where two related groups are not analysed together because
750 they are not recognized as potentially closely related.

751 (c) Conclusion

752 The morphological evidence available in the literature seems to support a bird origin for the
753 Palaeognathae. However, this evidence is outdated when viewed in the light of the present evidence
754 for a flightless LCA of the Palaeognathae. The tinamous are no longer considered sister taxon to the
755 Palaeognathae and no convincing evidence seems to exist anymore that can defend a flying LCA. All
756 morphological studies on the origin of the Neornithes assume a flightless LCA of the Palaeognathae,
757 which is evident from their systematic bias against large flightless taxa, as no analyses seem to exist
758 where both giant non-neornithines or giant Neognathae are included together with the giant
759 Neognathae. It is thus more than reasonable to doubt this hypothetical flying ancestry of the
760 Palaeognathae based on outdated biased datasets.

761

762 (2) Miscellaneous indications for a flightless origin of the Palaeognathae

763

764 Now that the tinamou can no longer be considered a missing link between a flying ancestor and the
765 ratites, evidence from phylogenetic studies where giant flightless taxa are systematically excluded
766 can hardly be considered strongly supporting evidence for a bird origin of the Palaeognathae. If no
767 phylogenetic analyses exist where it was attempted to answer this question, it becomes interesting
768 to explore arguments from very difficult angles. In additional file 1 (section IV, subsection 2), it is
769 suggested that branch lengths, a supposed continental flight loss of the stem Palaeognathae, the
770 'living fossil' phenomenon and the evolutionary rates of the Palaeognathae might present additional
771 indications in favour of a flightless origin of the Palaeognathae. None of these arguments necessarily
772 form convincing evidence to reject one or another hypothesis, but they still need to be taken into
773 consideration.

774 (3) Evidence from 'the old ways'

775 Almost a century ago, Percy Lowe (1928a) already opposed to the universally held idea that "the
776 flightless ratites lost their ability to fly in consequence of their restriction to insulated areas of land".
777 Lowe (1928a) had an opposing view on this matter and instead of derived adapted birds, considered
778 the ratites as 'living fossils'; "these insulated areas (...) represent the last sanctuaries which enabled
779 these relics of a primitive fauna to hold out for so long through geologic periods to which they were
780 not in reality adapted, and that by inference it was only a specialization towards a swiftly cursorial
781 habit of life which enabled to ostrich and the rhea to withstand the rapidly developed carnivorous
782 fauna of the Tertiary" (Lowe, 1928a). Lowe's work contains many references to previous authors
783 who argued that the ratites feature a 'degeneration' of wings, feathers, the patagium, the palate,
784 the keelbone and more, an idea to which Lowe (1928a) opposed. His hypothesis was that the ratites
785 never had a flying ancestor and that they possess many primitive characters, not different from non-
786 bird ancestors of the flying birds. He provided evidence for his views, based on the ratites'
787 distribution in space and time, their feather structure, the aftershaft, the patagium, the forelimb, the
788 palate, the sternum and more. His argumentation is too extensive to repeat in the present work, but
789 his views on the ratite feather structure can illustrate his reasoning.

790 Lowe assessed the complete absence of any pennaceous feathers (feathers with interlocking hooks
791 on the barbules) in the wing, tail or contour feathers for adult and juvenile moa, kiwi, emu,
792 cassowary, ostrich, *Rhea* and *Pterocnemia* (Darwin's rhea). Also filoplumes and plumules, two types
793 of feathers that are found commonly in the Neognathae, are completely absent in the ratites at all
794 stages of their development. The ratites only possess downy feathers, of which it is known that they
795 are the precursor to more specialized feathers in the ontogenetic development of the Neognathae.

796 The author held the firm belief that the complete absence of feather types that could form evidence
797 for a flying ancestry of the ratites indicates that these lineages simply never evolved to carry
798 pennaceous feathers, plumules or filoplumes. This hypothesis is in contrast to what his
799 contemporary colleague scientists argued, namely that these primitive feathers evolved by means of
800 a degeneration of ancestral pennaceous feathers. It has also been hypothesised that the many
801 'primitive' traits of the ratites could be considered a consequence of multiple events of neoteny
802 (retention of juvenile characters), an idea that was promoted by De Beer (1956), a view in which the
803 ratites are basically regarded as giant chicks. Lowe (1935) and Elzanowski (1989) argued against this
804 hypothesis of neotenic ratites. Even though a modern study has tried to find evidence for neoteny of
805 the development of the ratite wing (Faux and Field, 2017), conclusive evidence in favour of neoteny
806 has yet to be found. The conservative and parsimonious approach would be to assume that there
807 were no such multiple steps of neotenic evolution. A sixfold loss of flight feathers seems extremely
808 improbable, but even one single event of neoteny seems not supported by strong evidence.

809 The fact that there is absolutely no trace of flight feathers, not in the adult stage or any other stage
810 of their life cycle, forms an argument against a flying descent of the ratites (and an even stronger
811 argument against a sixfold flight loss). After all, the flightless birds from the Neognathae such as the
812 New Zealand Kākāpō still possess pennaceous feathers. Even the penguins still possess filoplumes
813 and plumules and contour feathers with hooked barbules (Cassondra, Hagelin and Kooyman, 2015),
814 showing evidence in their morphology of a flying ancestor despite being flightless for more than 60
815 million years. Only one example of a secondarily flightless neognath could be found which has signs
816 of severe degeneration of the pennaceous feather structure, namely *Atlantisia rogersi*, an island
817 inhabiting member of the Rallidae and the smallest flightless bird. Lowe (1928b) described that the
818 hooklets that connect the barbules of its feathers are 'ill developed' and that locally the barbules are
819 discontinuous, allowing free passage of air between them. Despite their fluffy looking plumage
820 reminiscent of ratite feathers, these pennaceous flight feathers of *Atlantisia rogersi* clearly show
821 structural evidence of its flying ancestors.

822 Aside from the feathers, the same reasoning is applied on other features that seem functionally
823 linked to flight such as the patagium, ossifications of the sternum related to the keel (lophosteon,
824 metosteon, urosteon), the pygostyle and the uropygial gland (Lowe, 1928a). All of the arguments
825 together convinced him to barely leave any doubt about his hypothesis. As he was not able to find
826 any indication of a flying ancestor in the morphology of a single ratite, he stated that the evidence
827 stands strongly in favour of a flightless non-bird dinosaur origin.

828 Lowe (1928a) did not go much into detail about the tinamous, as their phylogenetic position was
829 unclear at the time, with their mysterious mixture of neognath-like and palaeognath-like traits.
830 Some of the above traits that are absent in the ratites, are present in the tinamous, such as the
831 pennaceous feathers, the patagium, the keel and the uropygial gland. This can either be attributed
832 to an independent origin of the respective trait, or a sixfold loss of it in the ratites. The true
833 pygostyle however is absent in the tinamous and its possible implications are discussed in additional
834 file 1 (section II, subsection 8c). One other trait of the highest importance is feather structure. As
835 described before (section II, subsection 6), the tinamous possess pennaceous feathers with a
836 different mechanism of barbules attachment, which might or might not be an indication of a non-
837 homology.

838 It is interesting to keep in mind that during the time Lowe (1928a) wrote his work, no non-avian
839 dinosaur fossils were known that possessed wings and feathers, but were not equipped for flight
840 such as the evidence for feathers in the dromaeosaurs and oviraptorosaurs. Feathers and wings, no
841 matter how primitive, were still considered a feature exclusive to birds descending from a flying
842 ancestor. Contemporary scientists could thus have rejected Lowe his hypothesis with the simple
843 phrase “They carry wings and feathers, so they had a flying ancestor”. Furthermore, there was no
844 molecular data available that would suggest a sixfold loss of flight for the ratites. Back then, instead
845 of six, only a single loss of flight and a single event of neoteny (for multiple traits) were required to
846 explain the existence of the ratites. It is remarkable that despite this, Lowe was already fully
847 convinced that the Palaeognathae had no flying ancestors at any point, based on his morphological
848 studies on adult and embryo ratites.

849 (4) The giant Neognathae

850 If indeed the Palaeognathae never had a flying ancestor as suggested by evidence above, this has an
851 implication for the ancestral state of the Neognathae as well. Unavoidably, the first stem
852 Neognathae too would have been large flightless non-bird dinosaurs, which means giant flightless
853 Neognathae can be expected to exist, and to be assigned the status of stem neognath. Astonishingly,
854 fossils have indeed been found that match this description, and morphological evidence has
855 suggested a stem neognath and basal neognath affinity for these giant birds that might not be birds.
856 Morphological evidence from Worthy *et al.* (2017) has suggested a flightless origin of the
857 Neognathae based on a study with 290 morphological traits (Fig. 6). This phylogeny corresponds to
858 the third analysis of Worthy *et al.* (2017), an unweighted analysis on their full dataset with molecular
859 backbone enforced. Additionally in the present work, an ancestral state reconstruction of flight was
860 conducted by maximum likelihood in the software Mesquite (Maddison and Maddison, 2023) to

861 illustrate how this particular phylogeny suggests a flightless last common ancestor of the Neornithes,
 862 with an estimated probability of 0.994 that the last common ancestor of the Neognathae was
 863 flightless.

864

865

866 **Fig. 6** Most parsimonious phylogeny from the analysis of the full dataset of Neornithes with
 867 molecular backbone enforced from Worthy *et al.* (2017). Giant flightless taxa cluster together at the
 868 basis of this particular phylogenetic hypothesis of the Neornithes, suggesting a flightless origin of the
 869 Neornithes and some of its subclades. The extant members of the Anseriformes, Galliformes and
 870 Neoaves are collapsed for clarity, and an ancestral state reconstruction was added to illustrate how

871 this phylogenetic hypothesis suggests a flightless origin of the Neognathae, Palaeognathae and
872 Neornithes. Flying taxa are indicated in black, flightless taxa in white.

873

874 However, this hypothesis has been neglected by subsequent authors, in favour of the alternative
875 hypothesis which was given preference by Worthy *et al.* (2017). It is now generally believed that
876 those giant Neognathae must have evolved through different events of gigantism and flight loss, and
877 that they are not basal Neognathae, but rather belong to more derived positions, nested within
878 lineages of flying Galloanserae and Cariamiformes. The reason why this parsimonious phylogenetic
879 hypothesis was rejected shows how far-reaching the consequence is of making assumptions on the
880 flight state of the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae. After Worthy *et al.* (2017) found this
881 unfamiliar and rather incredible phylogenetic hypothesis (Fig. 6), they reasoned that the placement
882 of giant taxa as basal Neognathae and basal Neornithes was unexpected, and probably due to
883 convergent evolution of the giant Palaeognathae and giant Neognathae, called 'ratitization' in the
884 present work. They hypothesized that this convergent evolution caused the giant Neognathae to
885 cluster together at the basis in this phylogenetic tree. They then argued that because a flying last
886 common ancestor of the Palaeognathae is expected based on Phillips *et al.* (2010), Mitchell *et al.*,
887 (2014) and Yonezawa *et al.*, (2017), it is justified to remove all ratites from the analysis. This way, the
888 Palaeognathae become a clade of flying birds containing the tinamous and the Lithornithidae.
889 However, the present work has shown that all three references were not able to present convincing
890 evidence for a flying last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae.

891 Worthy *et al.*, (2017) redid the analysis after removing the ratites from the dataset, which resulted in
892 their fifth analysis, also unweighted and with a molecular backbone. Then indeed a very different
893 phylogeny was obtained (Fig. 7). This time, flying taxa are pulled to the basis of the tree due to their
894 similarity with the tinamous, which pushes the giant Neognathae towards derived positions in the
895 tree. An ancestral state reconstruction of flight was conducted in the present study by maximum
896 likelihood in the software Mesquite (Maddison and Maddison, 2023) to illustrate how this particular
897 phylogeny suggests a flying last common ancestor of the Neornithes, with an estimated probability
898 of 0.991 that the last common ancestor of the Neognathae was capable of flight. Since that moment,
899 these giant Neognathae have been recognized as derived members of the Galloanserae and
900 Cariamiformes and do not receive recognition as potential stem Neognathae and basal Neognathae
901 in the scientific literature. It seems like the phylogeny in Fig. 6 from Worthy *et al.* (2017) has been
902 rejected based on an assumption that was shown in the present work to be most probably incorrect.

904

905 **Fig. 7** Phylogenetic hypothesis from Worthy et al. (2017) after assuming that the last common
 906 ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a flying animal, justifying a removal of the ratites from the
 907 phylogenetic analysis. An ancestral state reconstruction of flight was added to illustrate how this
 908 phylogenetic hypothesis suggests a flying origin of the Neognathae, Palaeognathae and Neornithes.
 909 Flying taxa are indicated in black, flightless taxa in white.

910

911 Both figures illustrate how Worthy *et al.* (2017) presented two radically different phylogenetic
 912 hypotheses that require either multiple ornithization (Fig. 6) or multiple 'ratitization' (Fig. 7). They
 913 are undoubtedly correct to state that giant flightless taxa that evolved independently may appear to
 914 be closely related even if they are not. This could be caused by convergent evolution and character
 915 non-independence. But the same is true for lineages that independently acquired flight. This study
 916 clearly illustrates that large morphological datasets can return misleading parsimonious results.

917 Convergent evolution misleads us about the phylogenetic position of all giant flightless Neognathae
918 and about the flight status of the last common ancestor of the Neognathae and the Neornithes. It
919 was hypothesized by Worthy *et al.* (2017) that there is a misleading case of multiple ‘ratitization’, or
920 alternatively as suggested in the present work, a misleading case of ornithization with multiple
921 origins of flight. This example clearly shows that taxon exclusion or inclusion can cause a
922 ‘phylogenetic flight shift’ of the basal ancestral nodes of a tree. It furthermore shows how important
923 it is to not exclude giant flightless taxa such as *Gargantuavis*, *Patagopteryx*, the ratites and the giant
924 Neognathae in phylogenetic studies on the origin of the Neornithes.

925 ‘Ratitization’ was introduced in the present work as a hypothetical evolutionary step that combines
926 flight loss with gigantism from a smaller flying bird and loss of traits that are related to flight. The
927 generally accepted hypothesis of giant flightless animals within the Avialae includes not only six
928 events of ‘ratitization’ in the Palaeognathae, but also one for *Patagopteryx*, one for *Gargantuavis*,
929 one for the terror birds in the Cariamiformes, one for *Sylviornis* and *Megavitiornis* as a basal clade in
930 the Galliformes, and one for the demon ducks as basal anseriforms. In total these are eleven
931 hypothetical flight loss events with gigantism without taking the more controversial *Avimimus* into
932 account, or the possible flight loss of the lineage of *Brontornis*. As shown in the present work, there
933 is no strong evidence that the last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae was a flying bird, in
934 contrary. It was probably a flightless ostrich-like animal that originated earlier than previously
935 estimated. There is thus no strong basis anymore to reject the phylogenetic hypothesis (Fig. 6) that
936 came from the full dataset of Worthy *et al.* (2017) and bias this dataset by removing the ratites.
937 When the ratites are not being excluded, this particular dataset seems to suggest that the flying
938 Neognathae originated from flightless giants. This is precisely as was suggested by the hypothesis
939 presented in this work, namely that the last common ancestor of the Neornithes was a flightless
940 giant and that there was no flying ancestor in the stem Palaeognathae. Flight would have originated
941 somewhere in the stem neognath lineage, or once in the stem Galloanserae and once in the stem of
942 their sister group, or possibly even twice in the Galloanserae; once in the stem Anseriformes and
943 once in the stem Galliformes.

944 Considering the whole Avialae clade, the alternative for the eleven events of ‘ratitization’ could thus
945 be one origin of flight in the tinamou lineage, one or multiple in the Neognathae, and one or
946 multiple in the Mesozoic flying dinosaurs. That is at least three events of ornithization where
947 theropod dinosaurs independently evolved the ability to fly. It is hypothesized here that a full
948 ‘ratitization’ from a flying ancestor to a giant flightless one could correspond with a long branch of
949 similar length as a full ornithization from a flightless giant to a flying bird. If that is the case, a

950 phylogenetic analysis that includes all relevant flying and flightless taxa (instead of a dataset biased
951 against the giant taxa) should show a phylogenetic tree of the Avialae that no one has ever seen
952 before, where three to five ornithizations will be more parsimonious than eleven ratitizations. This
953 hypothesized 'phylogenetic flight shift' would be no different than the one discussed above in the
954 analysis of Worthy *et al.*, (2017).

955

956 V. A unifying hypothesis

957 (1) The differential extinction enigma

958 One last enigma needs to be addressed. It seems from many time estimation studies that several
959 lineages of the modern birds have survived the Cretaceous-Paleogene (K-P) extinction event. In the
960 recent time calibration study from Stiller *et al.*, (2024) where a maximum of the crown Neornithes
961 was imposed at 86,5 mya, it was suggested that two lineages of Neoaves crossed the K-P boundary,
962 as well as three lineages of Galloanserae and four lineages of Palaeognathae, making a total of nine
963 lineages. In other studies where a much older divergence prior for the crown Neornithes was
964 allowed, much older posterior divergence times were found for the crown Neornithes (Haddrath and
965 Baker, 2012; Wu *et al.*, (2024) and in the latter study up to 44 different lineages can be counted that
966 possibly survived the K-P extinction event. Furthermore in the present work, evidence was
967 presented in favour of the hypothesis that at least four (in the case that the Rheiformes are sister
968 group to the Dinornithiformes + Tinamiformes clade) but likely up to seven lineages of extant and
969 recently extinct Palaeognathae must have originated before the end of the Cretaceous to be
970 congruent with continental vicariance. Regardless of the exact amount of neornithine lineages that
971 survived this extinction event, the multifold survival of the neornithine lineages is in sharp contrast
972 to the complete extinction of all the non-neornithine avialans. There is no evidence that any of the
973 non-neornithine avialans (and other feathered dinosaurs) have survived the extinction event, even
974 though they made up the large majority of flying dinosaur fossils, compared to the near absence of
975 Cretaceous neornithine fossils in the fossil record (Hospitaleche *et al.*, 2024). The Enantiornithes in
976 particular were a most diverse and numerous clade of flying dinosaurs that seemed to dominate
977 avian ecological niches before the diversification of the Neornithes (O'Connor *et al.*, 2024). It would
978 be an incredible coincidence that all lineages of the numerous and diverse Avialae went extinct,
979 except multiple lineages of one particular subclade that is underrepresented in the Cretaceous fossil
980 record (Brusatte *et al.*, 2015, Hospitaleche *et al.*, 2024). This phenomenon deserves consideration,
981 and it is here described as a 'differential extinction enigma'. This differential extinction enigma could
982 explain why workers seem to try hard to keep the maximum divergence priors as close to the

983 minima as possible without any evidence, enabling them to obtain as much neornithine divergence
984 posteriors that are more recent than 66 Mya, but despite these possibly subjective efforts, a
985 remarkable differential extinction is still observed.

986 It is in the present work proposed that an explanation for this differential extinction may be found in
987 the geographical heterogeneity of the K-P mass extinction. It is possible that the most extreme
988 consequences of the meteor impact took place on the northern continents, completely eradicating
989 the northern dinosaurs in all their diversity. It is not unthinkable that the southern continents and
990 islands were relatively spared, with a larger diversity of surviving lineages. There are indications in
991 favour of this 'Gondwana refugium hypothesis'. The level of extinction at the end of the Cretaceous
992 is known to have been geographically heterogeneous depending on multiple factors such as the
993 distance to the Chicxulub crater, but also maritime and latitudinal buffering of the impact winter
994 (Bardeen *et al.*, 2017; Brugger *et al.*, 2017; Morgan *et al.*, 2022). Models based on these gradients
995 have predicted large extinctions in western North America and the Neotropics, but much less severe
996 extinctions in the maritime areas of temperate Gondwana (Wild, Carvalho and Stiles, 2023). The
997 same is suggested by the fossil record of macrofauna, microfauna and plants in the Antarctic region,
998 which lack an abrupt extinction horizon in Antarctic and Australian sediment (Crame 1992;
999 Zinsmeister *et al.*, 1989). It is thus possible that the extinction eradicated all dinosaurs in the
1000 northern continents, but that multiple dinosaur lineages with a Gondwana distribution were
1001 protected against the milder impact winter, for example by means of their feathers and their
1002 adaptations to long-lasting polar winters. If that was the case, the Neornithes could be considered a
1003 clade very similar to for example the Dromaeosauridae, Oviraptorosauria and the clade containing
1004 the non-neornithine Avialae, except that the neornithines got lucky to have been in the right place,
1005 at the right time.

1006

1007 (2) Introducing the unifying hypothesis

1008 The differential extinction of the feathered dinosaurs introduces the unifying hypothesis that is
1009 presented here. Many extant lineages of Neornithes have survived the K-P extinction event. This is
1010 attributed to a Gondwana distribution of most of the early Neornithes on continents and islands
1011 protected from the most disastrous consequences of the meteor impact that caused the mass
1012 extinction. The Neornithes would have been a clade of feathered dinosaurs with a flightless non-bird
1013 last common ancestor well before Madagascar became isolated from Gondwana. At some point
1014 during the Cretaceous, flight originated once or multiple times in a subclade now known as the
1015 Neognathae giving rise to the modern flying birds. Assuming the most recent molecular trees are

1016 correct, flight also originated in the tinamou lineage, somewhere after New Zealand split away from
1017 Gondwana between 82 and 62 million years ago. Both processes of flight origination are nothing
1018 more than an extension of the ornithization process that has taken place in different clades of
1019 feathered winged dinosaurs. After the end of the Cretaceous, all northern flying dinosaurs, mainly
1020 non-neornithines which were not closely related to the modern birds, went extinct. Possibly this also
1021 includes the extinction of some taxa related to the Neornithes that had already migrated towards
1022 the northern continents, such as candidate basal neornithine *Gargantuavis* and the neornithine
1023 *Asteriornis*. Soon after, the northern continents were colonized (or rather re-colonized) by those
1024 Gondwanan neornithines with the best flying capacities. The ones with the worst flying ability and
1025 the flightless ones remained restricted to their Gondwana distribution (Fig. 8). This applies to many
1026 of the most basal Neornithes when the phylogenetic hypothesis from the full dataset of Worthy *et*
1027 *al.* (2017) is followed (Fig. 6). That includes all members of the Palaeognathae, the stem neognath
1028 *Brontornis*, some stem Galloanserae such as *Patagornis* and members of the Dromornithidae and
1029 the stem Galliformes such as *Sylviornis* and possibly *Megavitiornis*. Even the basal extant Galliformes
1030 such as the Megapodiidae and the Cracidae seem restricted to Gondwanan regions, respectively
1031 Australia and South-America, and several authors have already suggested a Gondwana origin for
1032 these two families of crown Galliformes (Cracraft, 1973, Dekker 2007).

1033

1034

Fig. 8 Distribution of a selection of basal neornithines (plus *Patagopteryx*) on Gondwana land masses, suggestive of an ancient, flightless, non-bird and Gondwana origin of the Neornithes.

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1036

1037

(3) Remarks on a selection of Gondwana taxa

1038

Sylvionis and *Megavitiornis* appear to be stem Galliformes in the phylogenetic hypothesis from

1039

Worthy *et al.* (2017), see Fig. 6. *Sylvionis* from New Caledonia seems to fit the hypothesis of a

1040

Gondwana origin rather well, as New Caledonia itself is part of the continent Zealandia (Mortimer *et*

1041

al., 2017), the New Zealand continent. *Megavitiornis* however lived on Fiji, which is harder to explain

1042

in a context of Gondwana vicariance. Different authors don't seem to find agreement if Fiji was of

1043

continental origin or of oceanic origin (Segev, Rybakov and Mortimer, 2012). Older literature seems

1044

to favour Fiji as a continental part of the former Zealandia based on the presence of metamorphic

1045

rocks and granitoid plutons (Woolnough 1903; Crook 1963; Rodda 1967). Geophysical

1046

determinations and geological evidence from Robertson (1967) and Chase (1971) have led to the

1047 same conclusion. However some authors came to different conclusions and rejected a continental
1048 origin of Fiji, based on its small size and young visible rocks (Dickinson (1967) or pointing out that the
1049 crustal thickness on Fiji is typical for neither continental nor oceanic regions (Hamburger *et al.*,
1050 1990). They suggest that Fiji had an oceanic origin independent of the Gondwana landmasses.
1051 Everything taken into consideration, it seems not unreasonable to suggest a Gondwana origin of
1052 *Megavitiornis*, assuming that Fiji was at some point connected to Zealandia. It would seem far-
1053 fetched to hypothesize unexpected swimming capacities for dispersal by sea or two independent
1054 losses of flight and events of gigantism for *Megavitiornis* and *Sylviornis* and extinction of their flying
1055 relative.

1056 Another remark must be made about *Patagopteryx*, not to be confused with the crown neornithine
1057 *Patagornis*. *Patagopteryx* is the previously discussed candidate ratite from Argentina dated at 85
1058 mya. In the context of the hypothesis described here, it may well be a basal palaeognath based on
1059 the nine characters it has in common with ratites (Kurochkin 1995). The traits that were argued by
1060 Chiappe (1991) to be primitive compared to extant Neornithes may even indicate that *Patagopteryx*
1061 represents a stem neornithine. That would mean that both views (on one side Alvarenga, Bonaparte
1062 and Kurochkin, and on the other side Chiappe) made correct assessments on this taxon but they saw
1063 no way to unify their seemingly opposing views. This would make *Patagopteryx* a most curious fossil
1064 taxon, as it would represent a 'missing link' between the extant neornithines and the other
1065 dinosaurs. The same reasoning could work for *Gargantuavis*, which is suggested here not only to be
1066 a candidate stem palaeognath, but a candidate stem neornithine.

1067 Lastly, the ostrich needs a special mention. If the ostrich lineage originated through vicariance
1068 during the separation of Africa and the rest of Gondwana, firstly that would push back the time of
1069 origin of the Palaeognathae significantly, and secondly that would mean that it survived the meteor
1070 impact on the African mainland, in contrast to all other African dinosaurs. It is here proposed instead
1071 to follow an 'out of India' hypothesis, which is further supported by the findings of fossil ostriches in
1072 India (Buffetaut, 2022). Back when Gondwana vicariance formed the main hypothesis about
1073 palaeognath evolution, it was already hypothesized that the ostrich and elephant bird lineages co-
1074 existed on Indo-Madagascar (Jain et al., 2017).

1075 (4) The origin of flight in the modern birds

1076 In the light of the uncertainty on the origin of birds, the term 'birds' is here defined as all
1077 descendants from the earliest flying ancestor of the derived bird *Passer*, the sparrow. If the
1078 hypothesis that is presented here is followed, that would mean that the Palaeognathae and the
1079 giant stem Neognathae cannot be considered birds, and possibly neither the Galloanserae. The

1080 Palaeognathae would only have non-flying theropod dinosaur ancestors, meaning they are non-bird
1081 dinosaurs. Aside from an origin of flight in the tinamou lineage, the origin of flight in the other
1082 neornithines should be considered to have taken place somewhere along the stem Neognathae, or
1083 alternatively two or three times in the crown Neognathae. Similar to what was proposed in this work
1084 to be the mechanism of flight origin in the tinamou lineage, flight in the Neognathae could have
1085 evolved by means of wing assisted inclined running (WAIR). This behaviour has been observed in
1086 basal lineages of the Neognathae, such as in the Galloanserae (Heers *et al.*, 2014).

1087 (5) Less ratitization, more ornithization

1088 The flying Neognathae would have shown strong ornithization, leading to strong similarities with the
1089 tinamous and with the Cretaceous non-neornithine Avialae. The convergence between extant birds
1090 and other flying dinosaurs could be the cause why the Neornithes appear to be nested within those
1091 distantly related flying dinosaurs with a high consistency index and why their last common ancestor
1092 appears to have been a flying bird instead of a flightless feathered dinosaur. The hypothesis
1093 presented in this work thus suggests that science has been deceived for decades by ornithization.
1094 This exact deception has already been performed once by the tinamous, which were consistently
1095 found as basal clade of the Palaeognathae in morphological analyses because of the independent
1096 ornithization of the flying Neognathae and the tinamou lineage.

1097 (6) About rocks vs. clocks

1098 The origin of the Neornithes seems to have been remarkably older than the oldest neornithine
1099 fossils that are known to science. This mismatch has already been previously described in different
1100 time calibration studies, and has been called the 'rocks vs. clocks discrepancy'. For example in the
1101 study of Brown *et al.* (2008), even the youngest estimation of the age of the Neornithes was 38 mya
1102 older than the oldest undisputed fossil neornithine. Multiple explanations are here presented for
1103 this gap in the fossil record in the context of a Gondwana non-bird origin of the Neornithes. Firstly, a
1104 large part of Gondwana consists of Antarctica, where relatively few fossils have been unearthed for
1105 the obvious reasons of the ice-covered surface and the relatively low amount of fossil hunters on
1106 this continent. This could be considered a case of sampling bias that affects biodiversity metrics in
1107 the fossil record such as has been described for pterosaurs (Butler, Benson and Barrett, 2013), as
1108 well as ornithischian and theropod dinosaurs (Barrett, Alistair and Page, 2009). Secondly, it has been
1109 noted that the basal lineages of Neornithes consist of almost entirely terrestrial, nonmarine, ground-
1110 dwelling and heavy-bodied birds (Van Tuinen, Sibley and Hedges, 2000). It has been hypothesized
1111 that water birds have much higher probabilities of fossilizing than ground-dwelling birds (Benton,
1112 1997; Van Tuinen *et al.*, 2000) and that this differential fossilization could have caused a bias in the

1113 fossil record, explaining the paucity of basal and stem neornithine fossils. Thirdly, these early
1114 neornithines may simply have been much less abundant than other flying theropods, which could be
1115 expected if indeed their main diversification and accordingly their increased abundance occurred
1116 after the end of the Cretaceous. And fourthly, some fossils of flightless feathered dinosaurs that may
1117 belong to the stem Neognathae, stem Palaeognathae or even stem Neornithes are simply not
1118 recognized as such, as suggested in section IV, subsection (1). They have the potential to reduce the
1119 'rocks vs. clocks discrepancy' if an unbiased phylogenetic analysis could show that they are closely
1120 related or belong to the Neornithes.

1121 (7) Future phylogenetic work

1122 The only argument that remains against the hypothesis presented here is the phylogenetic position
1123 of the Neornithes nested within the extinct flying non-neornithine Avialae. It is hypothesized here
1124 that when the origin of the modern birds is investigated by means of a dataset without taxon bias
1125 against flightless giants, the Palaeognathae or Neornithes as a whole may no longer nest within the
1126 other flying Avialae. The most parsimonious tree might be one where three ornithizations follow
1127 from a flightless ancestral lineage, instead of eleven ratitizations from a flying ancestral lineage.

1128 In any case, the present work argues against drawing definitive conclusions on the origin of the
1129 Neornithes from morphological phylogenetic studies, as long as no unambiguous stem Neornithes,
1130 stem Neognathae and stem Palaeognathae fossils (Widrig and Field, 2022) have been identified.
1131 More generally, this work aims to underline the large responsibility of authors to formulate their
1132 conclusions correctly and objectively. Science can get constricted when authors jump to early
1133 conclusion based on lackluster evidence and the fields of morphological analysis and time calibration
1134 study may be especially prone to this. When the fossil record is highly incomplete, or when no
1135 evidence can be produced for maximum divergence times, scientists must interpret these studies
1136 with the greatest care and realize that they form no evidence strong enough to reject an alternative
1137 hypothesis.

1138 Future studies on basal avialans and basal neornithines must aim to test the hypothesis that was
1139 presented here, and no longer use the assumption that the last common ancestor of the
1140 Palaeognathae was flying bird. They must include not only flying taxa from early Avialae,
1141 Neognathae and Palaeognathae, but also flightless taxa.

1142 (8) Future ontogenetic work

1143 Future work in the field of ontogenetic development may further provide support for this
1144 hypothesis. The development of the sternum and sternal keel in particular could shed a light on the

1145 evolution of flight in the Neornithes. O'Connor *et al.*, (2015) have stated that the lack of published
1146 information on the development of the sternal keel of the Palaeognathae, and in particular the
1147 tinamous, is an important source of uncertainty when attempting to reconstruct the mode of sternal
1148 development in ancestral neornithines. They further state that if the sternum of the tinamous turns
1149 out to ossify bilaterally (in a 'reptilian' manner), as is only the case in the ratites and some non-bird
1150 maniraptoran dinosaurs, bilateral ossification will be readily interpretable as the ancestral condition
1151 of the Palaeognathae and possibly the Neornithes. No extinct or extant Neognaths are known to
1152 have possessed bilateral ossification of the sternum in combination with a keel. The authors
1153 suggested that this would be consistent with the possibility that this mode of sternal development
1154 was inherited from non-neornithines and even nonavian dinosaurs, and that the midline ossification
1155 present in the Neognathae and in the Enantiornithes maybe evolved multiple times. When the
1156 evidence from the present work is added to that, namely that the last common ancestor of the
1157 Palaeognathae did not fly, this bilaterally ossifying ancestral sternum of the Neornithes may indicate
1158 that the last common ancestor of the Neornithes did not have a keel and was not capable of flight,
1159 and that the tinamous may represent the first lineage, where a sternal keel develops despite this
1160 'primitive' mode of ossification.

1161 In the light of this hypothesis, it might also be important to conduct more work in the field of sternal
1162 ossification of non-Galliform birds. Most of what is known of avian skeletal formation is restricted to
1163 the single order of the Galliformes (Maxwell, 2008). This is described as a literature bias due to the
1164 fact that the chicken (*Gallus gallus*) and the Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix*) are used as model
1165 systems and have agricultural importance. The present work suggests that flight and thus a keel may
1166 have originated in the stem Galloanserae or in the stem Galliformes and stem Anseriformes,
1167 independently from the origin of flight of the other birds. The keel in these groups may be non-
1168 homologous. Because ossification sequences within modern birds are thought to be conserved
1169 (Starck, 1993, O'Connor *et al.*, 2015), a different developmental sequence of the keel between these
1170 groups may indicate a non-homology of the keel, and thus an independent origin of flight.

1171 (9) Taxonomic consequences

1172 If the unifying hypothesis receives support from the scientific community and if conclusive evidence
1173 for it would be found in the future, taxonomic changes will be required. Many taxonomic names
1174 have been based on the assumption that the extant birds originated from lineages of flying
1175 dinosaurs related to for example the Enantiornithes (Walker, 1981). As the unifying hypothesis
1176 contradicts this, the Neornithes (Gadow, 1892), meaning 'new birds', would have a name that is no
1177 longer appropriate for the crown dinosaurs, and some other changes will be necessary as well. It

1178 would seem appropriate to rename the Neornithes to “Gondwanasauria”, after their Gondwana
1179 origin and their diversification through Gondwana vicariance. However, the redefinition of the Aves,
1180 the Neornithes and some other taxa was removed from the present work after strong opposition
1181 from the four reviewers that have provided feedback on this work. First, consensus must be reached
1182 to preserve the stability and clarity of taxonomy.

1183 (10) A framework that makes sense

1184 The unifying hypothesis presented in the present work is able to resolve many unexplained
1185 phenomena. The tinamous would have earlier divergence times than what has been estimated
1186 before (Yonezawa *et al.*, 2017) and as a consequence their substitution rates may no longer be
1187 outliers with higher values than even the hummingbird. There would no longer be a requirement for
1188 the improbable and unparsimonious sixfold ‘ratitization’ in the Palaeognathae and up to eleven
1189 events of ‘ratitization’ among the Avialae. Additionally, there is no longer a requirement for multiple
1190 cases of neoteny to explain the feather structure, tail, palate, patagium and more in the
1191 Palaeognathae, some of which are linked to flight and supposedly took place six times within the
1192 Palaeognathae. Also, the absence of extant or fossil flying sister taxa to these flightless lineages, and
1193 with much better flight skills than the extant tinamous, would now be logical as these animals would
1194 have never existed. This would include flying stem ostriches, flying stem kiwi, flying stem elephant
1195 birds, flying stem casuariforms, flying stem moa from New Zealand, flying relatives to *Sylviornis* from
1196 New Caledonia and flying relatives to *Megavitiornis* from Fiji. Furthermore, the Gondwana vicariance
1197 hypothesis no longer has to be rejected. Under the unifying hypothesis, ‘Dollo’s Law’ is no longer
1198 challenged for the adaptations of flight or running-bird related adaptations because the ratites
1199 would not have a flying ancestor. Furthermore, the rather primitive burst-type flight of the basal
1200 neornithine clade of the Galliformes, for example limited by their anaerobic glycolytic muscle fibres
1201 (Butler, 2016), would represent an ancestral state of primitive flight instead of representing a
1202 degeneration from an ancestor with more derived flying capacities. The unifying hypothesis also
1203 provides an explanation for the differential extinction enigma as well as the differential fossilization
1204 of the Cretaceous neornithines versus the non-neornithine flying dinosaurs. No mechanism is
1205 required how the continental stem Palaeognathae would have lost flight in the presence of
1206 predatory dinosaurs during the Cretaceous, or alternatively how the rhea and ostrich went through
1207 continental flight loss as these flight losses did not take place. Also interestingly would be the non-
1208 homology of flight between the Neornithes and the Enantiornithes, which are characterized by an
1209 opposite articulation mechanism between the scapula and the coracoid. It is hard to imagine that a
1210 flying common ancestor of the Enantiornithes and the Neornithes, which already had a functional

1211 articulation of its scapula and coracoid as part of its flight apparatus, could bring forth two lineages
1212 with fully opposed articulation mechanisms. These 'opposite' flight mechanisms rather seem to
1213 suggest a non-homology of flight, which would be in agreement with the unifying hypothesis. And
1214 lastly, the long branches of the stem Palaeognathae and stem Neognathae each representing
1215 'missing links' of unfound fossils (Fig. S1) could finally be claimed by fossil taxa as discussed earlier.
1216 This way, the phylogeny of birds has transitional fossils from non-bird dinosaurs all the way to most
1217 derived modern birds, without these two large gaps. Most important taxa may be *Patagopteryx* and
1218 *Gargantuavis*. Instead of being non-neornithine members of the Avialae or being ratites, they might
1219 be stem Neornithes, forming a link between the extant dinosaurs and the other dinosaurs. That
1220 could explain why they seem to have a strong morphological affinity with the ratites, but at the
1221 same time possess characters that are considered primitive compared to the crown Neornithes.
1222 Equally important would be *Brontornis*, which may be a stem Neognath, and the other giant
1223 Neognathae which may also be link fossils on the evolutionary path towards flight.

1224

1225 VI. Conclusions

1226 First and most important, this work was able to show that no evidence seems to exist for the
1227 rejection of a flightless last common ancestor of the Palaeognathae, which is the most parsimonious
1228 hypothesis supported by the highest likelihood values as evidenced in this work. Flawed notions and
1229 reasonings have led to this unjustified rejection, such as the dubious application of Dollo's law, the
1230 inference from substitution rates that were calculated incorrectly by using fossil ages as maximum
1231 divergence times, and the wrong notion that vicariance and thus a flightless ancestor can be rejected
1232 by fossil-based maximum divergences posteriors. Furthermore, some workers in this field have
1233 systematically failed to recognize important evidence in favour of a flightless last common ancestor,
1234 such as recognition that a ratitization is much more than a flight loss. A sixfold ratitization in the
1235 Palaeognathae would encompass sixfold flight loss, (five to sixfold) gigantism, loss of patagium, loss
1236 of pennaceous feathers, loss of keel and much more. Additionally, authors who inferred a flying last
1237 common ancestor of the kiwi and elephant bird do not seem to have conducted the ancestral state
1238 reconstruction of flight, which would have illustrated just how unlikely this flying LCA is, with a
1239 likelihood value of 0.99996 for a flightless LCA instead as shown by the analysis of the present work.
1240 The present critical review paper has demonstrated that strong evidence in favour of a flightless last
1241 common ancestor, in combination with the total lack of evidence for a flying last common ancestor,
1242 could lead to the rejection of the latter hypothesis. As such, the continental vicariance hypothesis

1243 can finally be restored and the ratites no longer form a most extreme and most unlikely example of
1244 convergent evolution.

1245 Secondly, it was suggested that no study seems to exist which has properly tried to tackle the
1246 hypothesis of Percy Lowe, namely that the ratites are non-bird dinosaurs that at no point had a
1247 flying ancestor. It was shown how existing studies have been prone to bias, most importantly the
1248 bias where giant flightless taxa are systematically excluded from datasets. Now that the tinamous
1249 cannot be considered sister taxon of the ratites, the phylogenetic studies on the origin of the
1250 Neornithes are fully outdated due to their systematic bias against giant taxa. This is the case for
1251 giant flightless taxa from the non-neornithines, from the Neognathae and from the Palaeognathae.
1252 It was also illustrated how such bias can cause a phylogenetic shift in the ancestral flight status from
1253 flightless to flying (fig. 7 and fig. 8).

1254 The findings of this work were unified into a hypothesis that may prove difficult to reject. The
1255 Palaeognathae and large flightless basal Neognathae are proposed to be non-bird dinosaurs, and
1256 possibly the Galloanserae as well. Flight would have evolved in the Neornithes at least twice; once or
1257 more in the Neognathae, and once in the tinamou lineage. The Neornithes would have originated on
1258 Gondwana, where multiple extant neornithine orders would have originated during the Cretaceous.
1259 All flightless and flying dinosaurs in the Northern regions such as the flying Enantiornithes went
1260 extinct in the K-P mass extinction event. Many lineages of Neornithes, among which different bird
1261 lineages but also some non-bird lineages, survived the cataclysm due to the climatic isolation on
1262 Gondwana lands and islands, and thanks to their adaptations to survive in a cold climate. After the
1263 K-P mass extinction, the Neornithes with the best flying capacities (re-)colonized the other
1264 continents, whereas the others, mainly species from the most basal lineages, remained in their
1265 Gondwana lands, as can still be seen today in their distribution.

1266 In the light of this unifying hypothesis, any enigmatic aspect about the origin of the Palaeognathae
1267 and Neornithes seems to make sense, from their differential extinction at the K-P boundary, to their
1268 variety of primitive traits, from their Gondwana distribution to their low morphological and genetical
1269 evolutionary rates, from their long branch lengths to the existence of suspiciously ratite-like basal
1270 neognath fossils and suspiciously ratite-like non-neornithine fossils which seem so consistently
1271 removed from the few datasets that did not exclude the ratites already. Even though no conclusive
1272 evidence can be presented for this hypothesis as of today, the present work has presented small
1273 pieces of suggestive evidence that would seem to support this hypothesis. But the value of this work
1274 is not at all in presenting conclusive evidence. Its value is in showing that mistakes and circle
1275 reasonings have been made, and that no proper evidence seems to exist to reject a flightless origin

1276 of the Palaeognathae, which means mean that they might be non-bird dinosaurs. It is recommended
1277 that future phylogenetic studies take this hypothesis into account and that future data matrices are
1278 designed in such a way that this hypothesis will be properly tested.

1279 This work has two aims. Firstly it aims to show with convincing evidence that the last common
1280 ancestor of the Palaeognathae has been misinterpreted as a flying bird, but was most probably a
1281 flightless giant who dispersed most probably by means of continental vicariance. Secondly it
1282 provided a unifying hypothesis on the origin of the extant dinosaurs (the Neornithes) for which at
1283 present no convincing evidence can be present to support it, but more importantly, no evidence
1284 seems to exist to reject it. With this simple, conservative hypothesis that is able to form a framework
1285 in which all enigmatic aspects about the Palaeognathae make much more sense, it is aimed to spark
1286 a renewed discussion in the scientific community.

1287

1288 VIII. Additional material

1289 Additional file 1, doc file (.docx), additional text

1290 Additional file 2, text file (.txt), reduced dataset Livezey and Zusi for Fig. S1

1291 Additional file 3, text file (.txt), Palaeognathae molecular backbone from Mitchell 2014 Fig. S1

1292 Additional file 4, text file (.txt), Palaeognathae molecular backbone a from Stiller 2024 Fig. S1

1293 Additional file 5, text file (.txt), Palaeognathae molecular backbone b from Stiller 2024 Fig. S1

1294 Additional file 6, TREE file (.TREE), Phylogenetic tree mitochondrial dina Mitchell et al for Fig. 1

1295 ~~Additional file 7, text file (.txt), Dataset Lee et al for Fig. 2 and 3~~

1296 ~~Additional file 8, text file (.txt), Molecular backbone for Fig. 3~~

1297 Additional file 9, text file (.txt), Reduced dataset Livezey and Zusi for Fig 4 and 5

1298 Additional file 10, text file (.txt), Palaeognathae molecular backbone for Fig. 5

1299

1300

1301 IX. Declarations

1302 (1) Competing interests

1303 The author declares that he has no competing interests

1304 (2) Funding

1305 This work was realized without funding.

1306 (3) Authors' contributions

1307 This work was made by Koen A. Claeys.

1308 (4) Acknowledgements

1309 (...)

1310

1311

1312 X. References

1313 (references are for both the main text and the additional text see additional file 1)

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